

EFFECT OF TAX REVENUE AND GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMES) IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated the impact of tax revenue and government expenditure on the performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study is to evaluate the effect of Total Tax Revenue, to investigate the effect of Capital Expenditure, and to determine the effect of Recurrent Expenditure on Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. The researchers chose a mixed method research design to collect and analyze primary (qualitative and quantitative) and best suited secondary (quantitative). The population was 7,468 registered SMEs in Ibadan, a sample size of 380 was derived from the Taro Yamane formula at 5 percent level of significance and distributed equally across five urban Local Government Area through stratified random sampling. The required secondary data were collected from appropriate financial authorities covering the period of 2000-2024. The evinced panel least squares regression was employed using E-views version 13. The findings revealed the Total Tax Revenue ($\beta = -2.71E-05$, $p = 0.0000$) and Capital Expenditure ($\beta = -2.50E-05$, $p = 0.0000$) have negative and significant effect whereas Recurrent Expenditure ($\beta = 0.000114$, $p = 0.0000$) has positive and significant effect on SME performance. The R-squared was found to be 0.198989. The study concluded that fiscal components impacted SME performance significantly. Therefore, the study recommended that tax administration should be restructured to lessen onerous burdens on the SMEs and boost productive reinvestment.

1.0 Introduction

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) represent over 90% of the world's businesses and more than 50% of the jobs. SMEs are vital to the world

economy. Countries have contributed most in the development of innovative, varietal and robust economies based on knowledge and technological evolution. The performance of

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SMEs, on the other hand, is significantly affected by fiscal policy (taxation and government expenditure) which makes the environment, accessibility of resources, and competitiveness of the enterprise. In advanced economies such as the US and UK, sound fiscal frameworks that create tax efficiency while allowing productive government spending have encouraged strong SME sectors that make significant contributions to GDP and export earnings (Prince, 2025). In developing countries, however, heavy tax burdens, wasteful public spending, and weak fiscal institutions are often severely limiting the growth of SMEs and their contribution to national development (Udoh, Jonah, & Nyema, 2023).

Around the world tax revenue is one of the main fiscal tools that governments use to raise money for investment in public infrastructure and social services. Effective taxation provides public goods which enhance enterprises' performance, such as transport infrastructure, electricity, education, and health care. Yet, there is still much debate on the right mix of taxes and spending that avoids discouraging entrepreneurs. According to Keynesian theory, public spending, especially productive expenditure by the government, increases aggregate demand, employment and private investment while excessive tax impairs economic activity. According to Wagner's Law, as the economy grows, government expenditure tends to grow for a proportional basis. This happens because the demand for public services and infrastructure increases. These theories highlight the link between fiscal policy and

enterprise performance (Olusegun, Omotayo, & Olusegun, 2020)

Within Africa, SMEs play a pivotal role in job creation and poverty alleviation, Nonetheless, the composition of fiscal policy over time in many African countries has been marked by erratic tax regimes, inadequate capital expenditure and low spending efficiency. These issues have limited SMEs capacity to flourish especially those in commodity-exporting and foreign borrowing-dependent economies. The tax revenue of developing economies is essential for financing development and promoting growth but can be counter-productive when tax rates are excessive and SMEs are taxed multiple times (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022). Moreover, the government is misallocating its expenditure with more spending on recurrent as against capital expenditure and this has created infrastructure shortfalls and reduced business competitiveness.

Nigerian SMEs contribute to almost half of national GDPs and employ millions of people yet continue to perform poorly due to fiscal inefficiencies. Nigeria's public finance structure has been historically based on oil revenues, which have caused instability in government spending and inadequate non-oil revenue generation. Recent attempts to diversify have sharpened attention to taxation as a potential source of revenue. Nevertheless, tax policies' design and implementation pose difficulties for SMEs, among which are multiple taxation, lack of clarity and poor tax administration (Adewale & Oyedokun, 2022). Additionally, due to

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administrative costs and debt repayment, the governmental recurrent expenditure keeps on increasing. In contrast to this, the capital expenditure on infrastructure and SME was low (Imeokparia, Nnoli, Ojo & Ajibola, 2025).

In contrast, Ariyibi, Emily and Enitan (2025) showed that the components of fiscal policy like recurrent and capital expenditures do not impact SMEs' access to credit equally. The impact of each of these policy components depends on their particular direction and quality of implementation, there few studies on the interaction between tax revenue, government expenditure and performance of SMEs at the sub-national level in Nigeria in spite of these findings. Previously, most studies have looked into macroeconomic aggregates and neglected the context of small businesses. It operates under limitations in the fiscal environment determined by state tax administration and expenditure priorities. As one of the main economic hubs in Oyo State, Ibadan is a good backdrop for this. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the city are facing challenges arising from infrastructural deficiencies, multiplicity of levies and inadequate access to fiscal incentives essentially due to the government's revenue generation and spending pattern.

The study is important because it provides a detailed explanation of how fiscal policy instruments (tax revenue) will impact Small and Medium Enterprises' (SMEs) performance in Nigeria (Ibadan, Oyo State). Despite their importance for economic growth and employment supply, the sustainability of SMEs

rests on an enabling fiscal and infrastructural environment. The policy relevance of this study can assist government agency in restructuring its tax administration and realigning its expenditure patterns in a way that may improve the competitiveness, innovation and growth of SMEs. In practical terms, it can enable SME operators to have a better understanding of the impact of fiscal measures on their operations. In the academic plane, the research study helps in bridging both the theoretical and empirical gaps. It does so by integrating the primary input on the performance of SMEs with secondary fiscal data for the period 2000-2024. Furthermore, this research contributes significantly to the literature on public finance, development economics as well as entrepreneurship studies. The study investigates tax revenue, capital expenditure, and recurrent expenditure as independent variables while SMEs Performance is treated as the dependent variable. The study covers small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in the city of Ibadan in the manufacturing, trade and service sectors and utilizes registered as well as unregistered firms. Trends in data from 2000–2024 help to explain variation at the firm-level. Notwithstanding, the study might confront limitations like lapse in fiscal data, errors in responses and misleading temporal distortions owing to shock. Despite these limitations, the study was able to produce robust findings which contribute to both the academic and policy understanding of the impact of fiscal policy on SME performance.

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Consequently, Keynesian fiscal theories and Wagner's Law which essentially describe government spending as productive and fiscal growth as expansionary are the theoretical frameworks of this particular study. This study aims at bridging the empirical gap that exists by investigating the impact of tax revenue, capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure on the performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, and how fiscal instruments at subnational level operate towards entrepreneurial impact. The aim is to provide evidence-based insights to policymakers on how to design fiscal frameworks that can strike a balance between revenue mobilization and enterprise development.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, there has been an increased academic and policy interest globally regarding the impact of the fiscal policy, particularly tax revenue and government expenditure on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the developed economies, effective tax systems and productive spending by the public authorities have been important for SME growth. On the other hand, the fiscal policy framework of developing countries like Nigeria is associated with inconsistencies, inefficiencies, and inequities that continue to undermine the productivity and sustainability of SMEs (Prince, 2025). This irregularity in the fiscal situation is an issue because over 90% of business entities are SMEs and it contributes to job creation as well as innovation (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022). Tax revenue is the main source of public

finance but shows weak linkages with productive developments in Nigeria. Tax revenue performance indicators which are showing growth are Company Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), and Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) among others. In Nigeria, recurrent expenditure has consistently increased to 70 per cent and above of total expenditure. However, capital expenditure continues to be insufficient and fluctuating (Adegbie, Ogbebor, & Afokoghene, 2023). The lack of consistent fiscal coordination between tax collection and expenditure priorities has reduced the ability of the state to direct revenues into productive activities that can enhance SMEs (Adewale & Oyedokun, 2022). While some studies have examined the link between taxation, expenditure and economic performance in Nigeria, however, few have examined how these fiscal parameters jointly influence SMEs' performance in a specific local context like Ibadan. This poses a crucial research gap.

2.0 Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Concept of Small and Medium Enterprise in Nigeria

The picture of the productive sector of the economy is that of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) which plays crucial role in Nigeria. According to the World Bank, an SME is a firm with up to 300 employees and an annual turnover of less than \$15 million in Nigeria. Likewise, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria classifies SMEs based on assets and workforce capacity (Ariyo,

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2020). Most times, the typical SME in Nigeria range between 10 staff and up to 199 staff. According to SMEDAN and the National Bureau of Statistics (Nigeria), (2021). SMEs are responsible for approximately 48 percent of Nigeria's GDP. Additionally, they on near 96 percent of total businesses. In the opinion of (Bello-Olatunji, Oderinu, Olaosebikan & Aladejana, 2025), SMEs spur inclusiveness development and drive innovations and local productivity, especially in non-oil-performing sectors, conformable to SDGs. But for their survival and growth to happen, a conducive fiscal and infrastructural environment that improves access to finance, infrastructure, and markets is necessary.

Throughout history, the growth of SMEs in Nigeria was shaped through the instrumentality of various policy frameworks and institutional interventions aimed at promoting entrepreneurship and industrialization. SMEDAN was established in 2003 to coordinate the development of SMEs for the first time. Even with such initiatives, the industry is still impacted by policy inconsistency, underfunding, poor infrastructure and a burdening tax regime (Victor, Sylvanus, & Samuel, 2020). Study conducted by (Udoh, et al., 2023), it can be said that taxation and government spending are fiscal policies that affect the productivity of SMEs in terms of infrastructure and macroeconomic stability. The situation is same with (Chenge, Oigbochie & Udoh, 2022) as they found out that Nigeria's fiscal decentralization did not significantly translate to SME development as

there was inefficiency in revenue utilization and expenditure which was recurrently heavy thus constraining the growth of enterprise at subnational level.

Concept of Performance of Small and Medium Enterprise

The performance of SMEs from a multi-dimensional construct that impact the capabilities to generate profit, productivity, innovation, sustainability and growth in the economy. The performance of SMEs globally is seen as a key driver of competitiveness and inclusive development (World Bank, 2023). According to scholars (Bello-Olatunji, et al, 2025) the performance of SMEs goes beyond profit, as SMEs are able to adapt to changing market and policy conditions. SME performance in other high-income countries, relatively strong fiscal institutional support are important in providing access to finance, technology and skilled labour. On the other hand, the performance of SMEs in developing nations like Nigeria is hampered by fiscal inefficiencies, poor infrastructure, multiple taxation and limited access to credit (Victor, et al, 2020). The financial and operational performance of any firm in Nigeria depends greatly on fiscal predictability as well as efficiency in government expenditure which provides a conducive business environment, (Adewale & Oyedokun, 2022).

Over time, measurements of the performance of SMEs have changed. The earlier models focused on financial components like return on asset, profit margins, sales growth etc. But contemporary approaches incorporate non-

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financial metrics like innovation, customer satisfaction, corporate social responsibility etc. (Udoh et al., 2023). In Nigeria, performance assessment and benchmarking have been shaped by government support regarding infrastructure, fiscal incentives and market reforms. A study conducted by (Ariyibi et al., 2025) revealed that government recurrent and capital expenditures significantly impact SMEs' access to credit and the operational performance of SMEs meaning business viability is indirectly influenced by fiscal policy. Likewise, (Obiakpe, Empere, & Etale, 2025). A study, the effectiveness of government spending and the quality of infrastructure influences the performance of firms. This implies that fiscal management is an important determinant of sustainable SME growth (Hussain, 2024).

Concept of Tax Revenue

Tax revenues are among the most important instruments of fiscal policy. Furthermore, tax revenues are a major income source the government uses to finance development, ensure macroeconomic stability, and reduce inequality. Tax revenue reflects the ability of government to efficiently mobilize domestic resources to close the gap between public spending and the requirements of economic growth (Udeorah, Yusuf, & Amadi, 2023). In countries all over the world, they rely on taxes (e.g., personal income tax, corporate income tax, value-added tax (VAT), excise duties) to fund public infrastructure and social services. In Nigeria, however, the efficiency and equity of the tax system have been hampered by administrative inefficiencies,

evasion and corruption (Ajaero, Iheduru, & Uchegbu, 2025). The tax system in Nigeria has gone through continuous reforms targeted at improving compliance and expanding the tax net through initiatives like the Voluntary Asset and Income Declaration Scheme (VAIDS) and digital taxes. Though the measures have been put in place, the country's tax-to-GDP ratio is still one of the lowest in sub-Saharan Africa, indicating that fiscal mobilization underperforms relative to economic potential (Biwei, Awele, & Josiah, 2023).

Tax revenue refers to payments which individuals or business organizations are obliged to make to the government without receiving or becoming entitled to anything in return. In James, Adayinka and Idih (2019), the benefit and ability-to-pay theories suggest that taxation is a way of financing the collective need in proportion to one's income capability. Using the phrase efficient tax systems, empirical studies show that tax systems stimulate economic growth through financing of productive spending like investment in physical infrastructure, education and healthcare (Adefolake & Omodero, 2022; Ediri, Oliogu & Otejiri, 2025). But in Nigeria, wrong management of public funds results in taxes not being converted into anything meaningful. Omojola, Adebogun, and Audu (2022), opine that despite improved efficiency in tax collection as a result of financial inclusion and digital payment systems; weak enforcement mechanisms still limit effective fiscal administration. This raised many policy debates on aligning the tax structure and tax

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administration with long-term economic growth goals.

In Nigeria, revenue from tax is critical for both macroeconomic stabilization as well as development of small businesses and public investment. Studies undertaken show that different components of tax structure of a state exhibit different impacts on growth and enterprise performance. An example of bad news on taxation and economic growth is company income tax CIT. CIT has been found to have mixed effects on economic growth as firms are charged a compliance burden for meeting CITS requirements. In a parallel study, (Nchege, Aduku, Idika & Nwosu, 2019) discovered that tax revenue positively affects wage employment. Likewise, a more effective use of tax could lead to new jobs and higher productivity. Despite these developments, the Nigerian fiscal system will likely continue to face structural issues including narrow tax bases and overdependence on oil revenue. Consequently, tax revenue in Nigeria is not only considering SME performance but also the larger issues of fiscal sustainability, economic diversification, governance accountability, and more.

Concept of Government Expenditure

Government expenditure may be defined as the total amount of money spent by the state for the purchase of goods and services, building various kinds of infrastructure, and provision of social and economic welfare to the people. Taxation serves as a key tool of fiscal policy and a determinant of macroeconomic stability, job creation and sustainable development (Ejemezu

& Ajala, 2023). According to the classical thinking of Keynesians, government spending affects the total increase in demand, more so in a depression than any other item. On the other hand, Wagner's Law argues that as national income rises public expenditure would also increase because of the growing administrative and social demand. Subair (2019), asserts that Nigerian government expenditure is usually classified into two categories, namely, capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure. Capital expenditure refers to long-term investment involving spending on infrastructure and human capital. It also refers to which encompasses spending on wage, subsidy and other administrative spending. Aluthge, Jibir and Abdu (2021) revealed that productive public expenditure, especially infrastructure, education and health, directly affects economic performance and welfare of the citizens. However, inefficient government spending, corruption and misallocation of resources have undermined the developmental impact in practice.

In the history of Nigeria, the pattern of public expenditure has always been that of recurrent expenditure that exceed capital expenditure. This is despite the fact that the country always battles with infrastructural deficits and underdeveloped industrial capacity. In a study by Bello (2023), it was revealed that capital and recurrent expenditures have significantly affected GDP. The results suggest that recurrent expenditure has a more significant short-run impact on GDP. Further, it also suggests that

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capital expenditure has a greater long-run impact on GDP. As a matter of fact, the results of government spending on agriculture, health, and education will mostly differ in terms of economic growth based on the efficiency of this spending. Also, the efficiency largely depends on the degree of transparency in public financial management (Ugochukwu & Oruta, 2021). In a related study, Olaifa and Benjamin (2019) assert that while government capital expenditure encourages private-sector investment, the realization of the expected benefits has been undermined by the slow budget implementation and project execution.

Concept of Capital Expenditure

Capital expenditure is the government spending of funds on the purchase, construction or maintenance of physical and human capital assets. These are long-term assets. These are things that would make economy worthwhile when it is implemented to the nation. As per (Aluthge, et al, 2021), capital expenditure is significantly essential for sustainable economic growth as it expands the economy's productive capacity and creates employment. According to economists, this is a tool of fiscal policy which is in conformity with the Keynesian growth theory. The theory states that investing in productive assets increases demand in aggregate and output in the long run. In Nigeria, capital expenditure has remained an important factor in infrastructure development. Nevertheless, its contribution to the economy has been erratic due to poor implementation, corruption, and delays in budget execution (Bello, 2023). Capital

expenditure on the agricultural and manufacturing sectors significantly impacts GDP growth. Furthermore, the role of government investment in infrastructure (for example, roads, electricity, and technology) for industrialization is essential (Ikubor, Saheed & Oladipo, 2024).

In Nigeria's fiscal framework, capital expenditure is an important component which allows business enterprises, including SMEs, to develop at the micro-economic level. According to Anthony, Isma'il and Badara (2023), revenue inflows, especially from oil and tax, significantly impact capital budget performance, meaning public investment depends on the government's revenue mobilization capabilities. According to Udeh (2019), poor value-for-money assessment and weak monitoring frameworks undermine the efficiency of capital spending, thereby undermining its developmental impact. Moreover, the study by (Amadi, & Tubotamuno-Ojas, 2024) demonstrated that capital expenditures have a significant impact on the valuation of firms in the manufacturing sector of Nigeria. Productive allocation of capital spending will enhance the national output and value creation in the private sector. Thus, while capital spending is important for infrastructure and economic transformation, the impact of capital expenditure in Nigeria will very much depend on fiscal discipline and leak-proofing expenditure as well as institutional reforms.

Concept of Recurrent Expenditure

Recurrent expenditures refer to the amount spent by the government for getting day-to-day administrative work carried out (like salaries,

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pensions, overheads, etc.) in public offices/institutions and their maintenance. It is structured to guarantee the continual operations of government machinery and the delivery of public services (Ejem & Ogbonna, 2019) In terms of fiscal theory, recurrent expenditure refers to expenditure aimed at consumption which contributes to the efficiency of governance. However, it does not lead to the formation of capital over a long-term perspective. Countries all over the world are trying to find the right balance between recurrent and capital expenditures globally for fiscal sustainability. Similarly, in a less developed economy like Nigeria, the recurrent component always dominates the total expenditure.

Recurrent expenditure, in principle, means the non-investment cost incurred to the existing infrastructure, or funding public's salaries and government liabilities. Recurrent spending on internal security including salaries and pensions of security personnel, as well as other logistic costs, will have short term stabilizing effects and long term economic spillovers. George-Anokwuru and Inimino (2024), allocating too much to recurrent items limits fiscal flexibility and diverts funding away from productive investments (Raphael, 2021). Through evidence, it has been shown that while repeated spending on education and health enhance human capital development, the inefficiency with which such expenditures are managed often weaken the impact (Ogunjobi, Odusanya & George, 2024). According to a study by Onuaguluchi, Inyama and Oshim (2023), Nigeria's recurrent

expenditure is on the rise in spite of the introduction of the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) to curb wage leakages. The continuous imbalance in public finances highlights the need for expenditure rationalization for sustainable growth.

In particular, from a theoretical perspective, recurrent expenditure is based on the Keynesian notion that government consumption expenditure increases demand in the short run. However, when it is excessive or not accompanied by any complementary capital expenditure, it results in fiscal profligacy. The study conducted by Wayas, Onmonya, and Ebire (2024) identified that recurrent spending is negatively affecting the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria. Erasmus, Uwikor, and Fred (2023) find a positive relationship between recurrent expenditure and growth in the short run but the long run effects remain controversial as recurrent expenditure on the whole crowd out capital formation. Recurrent expenditure in Nigeria has a paradoxical meaning, as it is essential for a seamless governance and administration of activities; but it can be harmful.

Theoretical Review

Keynesian Fiscal Theory

British economist John Maynard Keynes, in his work titled *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money* (1936), put forth the Keynesian Fiscal Theory. The theory states that government intervention in and through taxation and public spending is important in attaining macroeconomic stability. This economic theory posits that the total demand in

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an economy drives the level of economic output and employment. Thus, during an economic slump, the government should increase its expenditure or decrease taxes in order to push demand and production (Chris-Ejiogu, Odinakachi, & Kalu, 2019). In Nigeria and other developing economies, expansionary fiscal policies enhance business activity by providing better access to infrastructure, credit, and market stability (Okoye, 2021). This theory is closely linked with the aim of the study in assessing the impact of total tax revenues and government expenditures on SME performance. The Keynesian model, despite its strengths, is limited in that it will lead to inflation, fiscal deficits, and debt accumulation if public spending is excessive or badly done. Despite this, the theory gives rise to the basis for assessing how public financial tools are capable of affecting production performance, business growth, and job creation of developing countries.

3.0 Empirical Review

Prince's (2025) study investigated Causal Links between Tax Revenue, Government Expenditure and Economic Growth in Nigeria, published in the African Journal of Management and Business Research. The study achieving the aim of finding the causality between Economic growth and Government expenditure. Using wavelet Granger causality econometric approach on monthly data from 1981 to 2020 the study finds that the two are bidirectional in long run. Moreover, the study also shows a one-way causation from real GDP to tax revenue. The outcome moreover revealed that tax revenue

affects government spending both in the short and medium terms. This means that Nigeria's fiscal sustainability depends on improving revenue diversification beyond oil. The findings of the study proposed that the Nigerian fiscal powers must strengthen her non-oil revenue sources so as to stabilize the flows of expenditure. The study also suggested that the Keynesian fiscal principles should be adopted in fiscal reform for the purposes of enhancing the productivity of SMEs and also macroeconomic balance.

The study of Ihekwereme (2025) on fiscal policy and economic stability in Nigeria, published in the International Journal of Human Research and Social Science Studies, employed the Keynesian fiscal framework, and multiple regression techniques to determine the impact of taxation and public expenditure on economic stability in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022. The study found that the petroleum profit tax, capital expenditure, and recurrent expenditure have a significant impact on the inflationary trend in Nigeria. In particular, the reduced capital cost did lead to lower inflation but recurrent cost and petroleum profit tax did. The study suggests reducing regular expenditures and boosting investment in productive sectors to ensure fiscal balance. The study strengthens the view that in addition to the prices of goods, fiscal policy will impact the SME through stable prices and investments in infrastructure.

Azebi and Akarara (2025) examined Macroeconomic Policies and Unemployment in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1981

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to 2023 and a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model in the AKSU Journal of Management Sciences. Authors found that increasing government expenditure, tax revenues, and money supply significantly reduced unemployment levels while raising lending rates increased unemployment. The researchers infer that expansionary fiscal policy (tax reforms and capital investments) can enhance employment generation through the development of SMEs. The findings of the study pointed out that public expenditure should focus on productive sectors to enhance job creation, which was directly relevant in understanding the impact of fiscal tools on the performance of SMEs through employment.

Jeff-Anyeneh and Ananwude (2025) have conducted a study on the Effects of Taxation on Government Revenue in Nigeria (2007-2023): Econometric Analysis (2025). The study, which used an ex post facto design and regression analysis, looked at the petroleum profit tax, the companies' income tax and value-added tax – and total revenue collected federally. The findings showed that although total revenue was significantly improved by the petroleum profit tax, VAT and company income tax were not. The study's findings show that expanding the base of VAT and improving administration of petroleum tax will enhance fiscal revenue. This suggests that the tax structure could determine government fiscal space, and the downstream impact is SME financing and infrastructure provision.

According to a study conducted by Titus, Ogbemor and Afokoghene (2025), which was published in The Economics and Finance Letters, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used by the researchers in investigating how different types of taxes affects employment, which extended from 1980 to 2023. According to the study, the tax revenue has inconsistent short- and long-run effects on employment levels because of a gap between Nigeria's tax policy and the present economic reality. The authors proposed a tax reform that aligns the way that revenue is collected in a way that effectively meets the productivity objectives of the economy, as well as, recommendations so that the fiscal space can strengthen the capacity of SMEs to absorb employment. Through the result of the study, we understand how an efficient tax system can promote SME-driven employment and national economy resilience.

4.0 Methodology

This study uses mixed-method research design with primary and secondary data to investigate the impact of the tax revenue and government expenditure on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria for the period 2000–2024. The study population was the 7,468 registered SMEs active in the Ibadan metropolis as reported by (Adewunmi, Abey, & Duru, 2024). The SMEs served as a valid sampling and reliable frame for the study. Due to the large population, the sample size was determined, using Taro Yamane (1967) formula for finite population which is expressed as.

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$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size (7,468), and e is the level of precision (0.05).

Thus, the sample size is:

$$n = \frac{7468}{1 + 7468(0.05)^2} = \frac{7468}{19.67} \approx 380 \text{ SMEs}$$

In order to achieve a fair representation across the urban commercial hub of Ibadan, a stratified sampling technique was adopted. This sampling technique focused on the five urban Local Government Areas like Ibadan North, Ibadan North-East, Ibadan North-West, Ibadan South-West and Ibadan South-East. The total sample of 380 SMEs was equally distributed in the five LGAs so that there was 76 SMEs in each LGA (380 ÷ 5). Simple random sampling was then used within each stratum to select participating firms. The primary data for the study was collected through the use of structured closed-ended questionnaires to measure retrospective performance indicators among SMEs.

Meanwhile secondary data measuring tax revenue, capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure from 2000 to 2024 was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, Federal Inland Revenue Service and the National Bureau of Statistics of Nigeria. Data was analyzed using panel least squares regression in EViews (version 13) based on the model

$$SMEP_{itk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAXREV_t + \beta_2 CAPEXP_t + \beta_3 RECEXP_t + \mu_i + \varepsilon_t,$$

Where SMEP represents SME performance, TAXREV total tax revenue, CAPEXP capital expenditure, RECEXP recurrent expenditure, μ_i firm-specific effects, and ε_t the error term, thereby ensuring statistical rigor and robust inference on the fiscal determinants of SME performance in urban Ibadan.

5.0 Results and Discussion

The results and discussion of this study was based on the interpretation of the descriptive and inferential statistics results obtained from the method of data analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables under Study

Statistics	SMEP	TAXREV	CAPEXP	RECEXP
Mean	3.597105	22635.38	22868.09	7708.731
Median	3.561423	21651.80	16865.15	4568.629
Maximum	4.847274	55531.00	59654.41	21752.38
Minimum	2.375000	3373.700	3832.800	1592.464
Std. Dev.	0.508656	17886.62	19821.44	7209.047
Skewness	0.351558	0.934531	1.021603	1.311940
Kurtosis	2.650814	2.600586	2.601908	3.009418
Jarque-Bera	46.22279	273.9691	324.9876	516.3630
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	6474.788	40743684	41162562	13875715
Sum Sq. Dev.	465.4565	5.76E+11	7.07E+11	9.35E+10

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Observations	1800	1800	1800	1800
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**Source: Researcher Compilation
Extracted from E views Version 13**

Table 1: shows the descriptive statistics of Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, Tax Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and Recurrent Expenditure over 1,800 observations. The study period has an average score of 3.597105 on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises indicating moderate to good performance. The number against it seems to be low due to this standard deviation value. The 0.351558 value for skewness shows slight positive skewness however, the probability from the Jarque-Bera test shows that the difference from normality is significant. The performance variable exhibits consistency; however, it does not follow a normal distribution.

Table 1 shows that the mean value for Tax Revenue is 22635.38. This indicates high levels of this revenue within the study period. The standard deviation of 17,886.62 which is quite high implies variations in revenue generation. Having a skewness of 0.934531 refers to moderate positive skewness for money stock of the country. The Jarque-Bera probability is

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Correlation Probability	SMEP	TAXREV	CAPEXP	RECEXP
SMEP	1.000000			

0.000000 which indicates that the series is not normally distributed. Tax Revenue, therefore, shows massive variations and departs from normality in the period studied.

The Capital Expenditure mean value of 22,868.09 is a good approximation of the mean level of Tax Revenue (Table I). Nevertheless, the standard deviation of 19,821.44 suggests a significant variation in government capital spending. The presence of a skewness value 1.021603 and a Jarque-Bera probability value 0.000000 indicates a positive skewed and non-normal distribution. Hence, Capital Expenditure displays significant variation and is non-normal. To conclude, the mean of Recurrent Expenditure is 7,708.731 which was lower than both Tax Revenue and Capital Expenditure. Hence, it indicates a relatively insignificant outlay. There is a lot of deviation as the standard deviation is 7209.047. The skewness value of 1.311940 indicates the positive skewness of data. Also, Jarque-Bera probability value of 0.000000 indicates that data is not normally distributed. As a result, Recurrent Expenditure was highly volatile and does not follow normality.

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TAXREV	----- -0.337860	1.000000		
	0.0000	-----		
CAPEXP	-0.321763	0.987796	1.000000	
	0.0000	0.0000	-----	
RECEXP	-0.269616	0.974607	0.984722	1.000000
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-----

**Source: Researcher Compilation
Extracted from E views Version 13**

Table 2: reveals how Performance of SSME was associated with Tax Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and Recurrent Expenditure. Another calculation using the regression output was the correlation coefficient with the two variables being Tax Revenue and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. The value for the coefficient here is -0.337860 . The probability value or the p-value here is 0.0000 which indicates significance. Thus, by our interpretation, a one unit increase in Tax Revenue is associated with a 0.337860 decrease in Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. Also, Capital Expenditure possesses a negative beta value of -0.321763 at probability

0.0000 indicating that as Capital Expenditure was increased by one unit SME performance decreases by 0.321763 unit and the relationship is significant. Similarly, we find that Recurrent Expenditure has a beta value of -0.269616 . Also, the probability of this value is 0.0000 . This means that the increase of one unit of Recurrent Expenditure will result in a decrease of 0.269616 in the performance of SMEs. Moreover, this relationship is statistically significant. Moreover, the fiscal variables are found to exhibit extremely high positive correlation with each other with beta values being above 0.97 and probability value being 0.0000 . The correlation results show that all fiscal variables significantly and inversely relate to SME performance while also strongly and positively relating to each other.

Table 3: Regression Summary (Dependent Variable: SME Performance)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 02/12/26 Time: 11:54

Sample: 1 1800

Included observations: 1800

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
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C	3.901819	0.019150	203.7456	0.0000
TAXREV	-2.71E-05	3.87E-06	-7.005626	0.0000
CAPEXP	-2.50E-05	4.49E-06	-5.571281	0.0000
RECEXP	0.000114	8.58E-06	13.30321	0.0000
R-squared	0.198989	Mean dependent var		3.597105
Adjusted R-squared	0.197651	S.D. dependent var		0.508656
S.E. of regression	0.455623	Akaike info criterion		1.267917
Sum squared resid	372.8356	Schwarz criterion		1.280129
Log likelihood	-1137.125	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.272425
F-statistic	148.7225	Durbin-Watson stat		1.350810
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher Compilation

Extracted from E views Version 13

Table 3 depicts the regression estimates regarding the effect of Tax Revenue and Capital and Recurrent Expenditure on Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. The constant has an unstandardized coefficient of 3.901819, t-statistic of 203.7456, and probability value of 0.0000. As per the regression results when both Tax Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and Recurrent Expenditure are held constant the expected level of Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises will be 3.901819 and this intercept is statistically significant at 1 percent level. Tax Revenue records a coefficient of -2.71E-05 with a t-statistic of -7.005626 and a probability value of 0.0000, implying that a one increase in Tax Revenue leads to a 0.0000271

decrease in Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, and this negative effect is statistically significant. Capital Expenditure has a coefficient of -2.50E-05 with a t-statistic of -5.571281 and a probability value of 0.0000, meaning that a one increase in Capital Expenditure results in a 0.0000250 decrease in Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, and the effect is statistically significant. Recurrent Expenditure shows a coefficient of 0.000114 with a t-statistic of 13.30321 and a probability value of 0.0000, indicating that a one increase in Recurrent Expenditure increases Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises by 0.000114, and this positive effect was statistically significant. The R-squared value of 0.198989 indicates that 19.90 percent of the variation in Performance of Small and Medium

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Enterprises was explained by the independent variables, while the adjusted R-squared of 0.197651 confirms the stability of the model after adjustment. The F-statistic of 148.7225 with a probability value of 0.000000 indicates that the overall regression model was statistically significant. Therefore, the regression results confirm that Tax Revenue and Capital Expenditure exert significant negative effects, while Recurrent Expenditure exerts a significant positive effect on Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises.

Testing of Hypotheses

The hypotheses of this study are tested using the regression coefficient results presented in Table 3. The decision rule states that the null hypothesis will be rejected if the probability value is less than 0.05 and accepted if otherwise.

Hypothesis One

Ho1: Total Tax Revenue has no significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 3 shows that the probability value for Total Tax Revenue is 0.0000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, Total Tax Revenue has a significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Hypothesis Two

Ho2: Capital Expenditure has no significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 3 shows that the probability value for Capital Expenditure is 0.0000, which is less than

the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, Capital Expenditure has a significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Hypothesis Three

Ho3: Recurrent Expenditure has no significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 3 shows that the probability value for Recurrent Expenditure is 0.0000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, Recurrent Expenditure has a significant effect on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State.

6.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of Tax Revenue and Government Expenditure on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. In line with the first objective, which sought to evaluate the effect of total tax revenue on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, the regression findings revealed that Total Tax Revenue exerts a statistically significant negative effect on SME performance. This implies that increases in total tax revenue, within the context of the study area, are associated with reductions in SME performance indicators. The research question regarding whether total tax revenue significantly influences SME performance is therefore answered in the affirmative, though in an adverse direction. This finding corroborates Adanlawo and Vezi-Magigaba (2022), who

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reported that tax policies impose significant constraints on SME growth in Nigeria, and aligns with Adewale and Oyedokun (2022), who found that certain corporate taxes negatively affect SME financial performance.

With respect to the second objective, which aimed to investigate the effect of capital expenditure on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, the results indicated that Capital Expenditure has a statistically significant negative effect on SME performance within the model. This suggests that increases in capital expenditure, as currently structured and implemented, have not translated into measurable improvements in SME performance in the study area. The corresponding research question is thus resolved by establishing that capital expenditure significantly influences SME performance, but not in a growth-enhancing manner. This outcome is consistent with the position of Bello (2023), who observed that capital expenditure does not always yield sustainable growth outcomes in Nigeria due to implementation inefficiencies, and it further resonates with (Ariyibi, et al, 2025), who reported mixed fiscal effects on SME performance.

Regarding the third objective, which sought to determine the effect of recurrent expenditure on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, and the findings revealed that Recurrent Expenditure exerts a statistically significant positive effect on SME performance. This indicates that increases in recurrent expenditure are associated with

improvements in SME performance indicators within the study period. The research question relating to the significance of recurrent expenditure was answered positively. This finding was in line with Erasmus, Uwikor, and Fred (2023), who found that public expenditure contributes positively to economic development in Nigeria, and it aligns with Ejemezu and Ajala (2023), who reported that government expenditure supports socio-economic outcomes when effectively utilized. Overall, the study concludes that tax policy and government expenditure significantly influence the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, though the direction of influence varies across Total Tax Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and Recurrent Expenditure.

7.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained, this study offers useful recommendations to policymakers, fiscal authorities, operators of SMEs and other interested parties in Ibadan metropolis and the Nigerian economy at large.

In the first place, since there is a considerable negative influence of total tax revenue on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, authorities responsible for fiscal policies should reposition tax administration so as to minimize excessive burden on SMEs, streamline compliance processes, and expand targeted tax reliefs and incentives that would enhance the profitability and reinvestment capacity of SMEs.

Also, since capital expenditure significantly has a negative impact on the Performance of Small and

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Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, and Government should ensure efficiency, transparency, and monitoring in the execution of capital projects so that the capital projects translate into improvement in power supply, transportation, market access favorable to the operations of SMEs.

In light of the positive and significant influence of recurrent expenditure on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, the government should continue and

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target recurrent spending towards development-oriented management services, regulatory assistance, and institutional frameworks that promote business stability and operational continuity.

Ultimately, there's a need for a unified fiscal framework that is designed from the perspective of Total Tax Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and Recurrent Expenditure. This is to ensure that all revenue mobilization is targeted at the objective of SME development.

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